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Islamic social finance: trends and issues

KEYWORDS

Islamic social
finance,
literature review,
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analysis

ABSTRACT

Introduction. COVID-19 shocks the economic stability worldwide. Governments take action to survive and to recover from the pandemic. Awareness towards alternative finance to recover the national and global economy. Islam has introduced social modes of financing. Research on Islamic social finance has also been performed from various aspects and methods. This study analyses trends, reviews systematically, and provides future direction for research related to Islamic social finance studies.

Materials and Methods. Scopus Indexed articles will be analyzed to achieve the objective of the study. Systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis are implemented to answer the research questions.

Results. The results showed that research related on Islamic social finance covers wide variety of topics. Both development of zakat and waqf related discussion has been progressing and the number of research studying these issues are rising. Since the emergence of COVID-19, the study on finding alternative source of financing is increasing. Integration of commercial and social finance could be among the solutions. Therefore, it needs to be studied more to propose new and more innovative models.

Conclusion. Future discussion on positioning zakat and waqf as formal national source of financing is still needed. Methods and points of discussion on zakat and waqf in other countries could adopt and imitate those implemented in countries which have been studied frequently such as Malaysia and Indonesia.

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INTRODUCTION

1. Background

COVID-19 shocks the economic stability worldwide. Governments take action to survive and to recover from the pandemic. Awareness towards alternative finance to recover the national and global economy. At national and international level, governments worldwide issue bonds in national and international currency. At society level, physical donations and financial crowdfunding are promoted massively.

Islam has introduced social modes of financing since its first inception. Other than commercial contract such as mudharaba (capital-labor agreement), musharaka (both capital labor participation from partners), muzaraah (capital-labor agreement for agriculture partnership), salam (purchase order with upfront payment agreement), istisna (purchase order with payment upon product delivery agreement), ijarah (leasing contract), and bai (sale) contract, there are social payment such as zakat and waqf donation. Both were source of national income in the time of Prophet Muhammad PBUH and the Muslim Caliphates. Zakat is obligatorily paid with certain amount and certain recipients according to the stipulated provision. Waqf in other hand is voluntary and has no provision as to how much and how often to be paid. Therefore, it has more flexibility.

Research on Islamic social finance has also been performed from various aspects and methods. Systematic literature review has been conducted on either zakat or waqf studies.

Aldeen [3], Alshater et.al [5; 6], Nawi et.al [18], Ninglasari [19], Rahmalan & Hussin [23], Rusydiana [26; 28], Rusydiana & As Salafiyah [27], Uluyol [30], Uluyol et.al [31], Yusuf et.al [34] studied on waqf research. Aldeen [3] covered articles publication period as the object of the analysis is 40 years while Uluyol [30] and Uluyol et.al [31] covered 30 years of publication. Alshater [5] and Nawi et.al [18] conducted bibliometric review on waqf study. Rahmalan & Hussin [23] focus on innovative waqf sources. Rusydiana [26; 28] analysed Scopus indexed articles.

Alshater et.al [6], Firmansyah [10], Hudaefi et.al [11], Nailah & Rusydiana [17], Nisywah [20], Paizin [21], Rusydiana & As Salafiyah [27], and Yusuf et.al [35] studied on zakat research. Firmansyah et.al [10] focus on articles published in Indonesia.

Hudaefi et.al [11] and Rusydiana & As Salafiyah [27] focus on zakat studies during COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia. Nailah & Rusydiana [17] discuss on Zakat and Technology. Niswah [20] studied on zakat research in ASEAN. Paizin et.al [21] used Scopus Database as the articles source. Previous studies analysed waqf and zakat separately.

Because zakat and waqf are both under same broader topics which is Islamic Social Finance, some authors wrote both on zakat and waqf. Among those are Alshater (singled author, 2021b; and et.al, 2021) and Rusydiana [26; 27; 28], Yusuf et.al [34; 35], conducted review on both zakat and waqf research This study will analyse trend on zakat and waqf research together.

This study analyses trends, reviews systematically, and provides future direction for research related to Islamic social finance studies, both covering and comparing zakat and waqf research.

2. Objective

In this study, we deploy the bibliometric and network analyses to fulfil the needs of such a systematic review. It is widely known that bibliometric and network analyses are among the powerful techniques to identify and cluster the area of research, which can lead to insightful follow-up analysis. Hence, the objective of this paper is to review research written on Islamic Social Finance covering zakat and waqf.

METHODOLOGY

The bibliometric analysis is a systematic analytical technique to identify the most influential authors, their affiliations, the keywords they use and more importantly how these attributes link one work to the other. The network analysis, on the other hand, is a rigorous method to determine the cluster of the research areas, thus revealing the directions and gaps in the future research. The systematic guidelines for the bibliometric analysis by Fahimnia, Sarkis and Davarzani (2015) and network analysis using VOSviewer by Cancino, Merigo, Coronado, Dessouky and Dessouky (2017) were adopted in this research.

This study is conducted to attain the big picture of research in Islamic social finance. The procedures are comprehensively performed using iterative cycles of defining relevant and informative keywords, querying the literature database, and

performing rigorous analytics (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). We adopted a review of research methods from Fahimnia et al. (2015) and Wamba and Mishra (2017), in which a five-stage research method to achieve similar study objectives are proposed. These five stages are as follows: (1) defining search terms, (2) including-and-excluding articles, (3) selecting the process of articles, (4) performing preliminary data analysis and (5) conducting bibliometric and network analysis. We elaborate each of these stages to assure the validity of our findings and to enable the readers to implement this method for systematically performing an analysis-based literature review in their study.

1. Data

Scopus is chosen for certain criteria. In some countries, this database is the minimum requirement for academic related administration matter. The search terms or the keywords used for data collection are “zakat”, “waqf”.

2. Method

Harzing Publish or Perish is utilized in the searching process. Using these search terms, we query the database and perform our next stage. For wider coverage, the search was not limited only for journal article. The search results including essential attributes of the articles, such as the name of the author(s), title, year, citation count, affiliations, abstracts, keywords and references were stored in RIS format for analytical purposes. By further processing the query results, we removed article duplication. We also exclude news articles, and some papers in non English language such as German, Korean, and Japanese. News are excluded for the relatively short coverage of the discussion, while non English articles are excluded for technical reason related to the cluster mapping based on keywords. The final number was reduced into 358 articles. The bibliometric analysis uses VOSviewer.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

1. Statistical Results

Total number of articles found using the keywords are 184 articles for selected publication on “zakat” and 174 selected articles for “waqf.” Frequency of articles with the chosen keywords based on year published is as follows:

Figure 1 Frequency for Zakat Articles by Year

Up until 2001, there was only one Scopus indexed publication written on Zakat on average between 1969-2001. The trend is then increasing after that and reach the peak in 2018 by 26 articles.

Figure 2 Frequency for Waqf Articles by Year

The trend is quite similar for waqf articles, with only slight difference. Up until 1990s, there were roughly only one publication per year. Similar to zakat articles, the peak number is reached in 2018 by 22 articles.

The distribution of articles based on the top citations is as follow:

Table 1

Top Zakat Articles based on Number of Citation

Cites	Authors	Title	Year	Source
108	J.C. Scott	Resistance without Protest and without Organization: Peasant Opposition to the Islamic Zakat and the Christian Tithe	1987	Comparative Studies in Society and History
53	N. Wahab	A framework to analyse the efficiency and governance of zakat institutions	2011	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
39	T. Kuran	Islamic redistribution through zakat historical record and modern realities	2003	Poverty and Charity in Middle Eastern Contexts
36	M.R.B. Rosli	Distribution management of zakat fund: Recommended proposal for asnaf riqab in Malaysia	2018	International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology
32	M. Mohit	Social housing programme of Selangor Zakat Board of Malaysia and housing satisfaction	2011	Journal of Housing and the Built Environment
29	A. Ab Rahman	Zakat institution in Malaysia: Problems and issues	2012	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah
23	J. Al-Ajmi	Decisions on capital structure in a Zakat environment with prohibition of riba: The case of Saudi Arabia	2009	Journal of Risk Finance
23	K. Retsikas	Reconceptualising Zakat In Indonesia: Worship, philanthropy and rights	2014	Indonesia and the Malay World
23	I. Ali	Zakat as a poverty reduction mechanism among the muslim community: Case study of Bangladesh, Malaysia, and Indonesia	2014	Asian Social Work and Policy Review
22	M. Yusuf	Measurement model of corporate zakat collection in Malaysia: A test of diffusion of innovation theory	2013	Humanomics

The highest cited paper belongs to J. C. Scott [29] with 108 citations. Article titles "Resistance without Protest and without Organization: Peasant Opposition to the Islamic Zakat and the Christian Tithe" was published in 1987 in Comparative Studies in Society and History. The second on the list is A framework to analyse the efficiency and governance of zakat institutions by N. Wahab.

All articles with top citation are conceptual papers. Most of the object of the studies are in Malaysia. Topics varied covering conceptual and empirical studies.

Among topics for conceptual papers are Zakat as poverty reduction mechanism in muslim country (Ali, [4]), how zakat should be reconceptualized especially for muslim majority populated country like Indonesia (Retsikas, [24]), comparing past and current practices on zakat implementation (Kuran, [12]). Several studies also discuss on problems and challenges such as issues on zakat institution (Ab Rahman, [1]), opposition to the zakat management (Scott, [29]). Some other studies propose for zakat efficiency analysis (Wahab, [32]), zakat distribution for riqab (Rosli et al., [25]), and measurement for corporate zakat (Yusuf, 2013). Among empirical studies are Al Ajmi [2] which discusses on the effect on zakat and capital structure in Saudi Arabian companies and Mohit [15] which analyses response for social housing program provided by Zakat Institution in Malaysia.

Table 2

Top Waqf Articles based on Number of Citation

Cites	Authors	Title	Year	Source
156	T. Kuran	The Provision of Public Goods under Islamic Law: Origins, Impact, and imitations of the Waqf System	2001	Journal of the Law and Society Association
81	J. Mandaville	Usurious Piety: The Cash Waqf Controversy in the Ottoman Empire	1979	Source: International Journal of Middle East Studies
68	A.M. Sadeq	Waqf, perpetual charity and poverty alleviation	2002	International Journal of Social Economics
44	B. Doumani	Endowing family: Waqf, property devolution, and gender in greater Syria, 1800 to 1860	2004	Society for Comparative Study of Society and History
42	M. Ismail Abdel Mohsin	Financing through cash-waqf: a revitalization to finance different needs	2013	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management
41	M. Shatzmiller	Islamic Institutions and Property Rights: The Case of the 'Public Good' Waqf	2001	Source: Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient
37	H. Yayla	Operating regimes of the government: Accounting and accountability changes in the sultan süleyman waqf of the ottoman empire (the 1826 experience)	2011	Accounting History
35	G. Baer	The Waqf as a Prop for the Social System (Sixteenth-Twentieth Centuries)	1997	Source: Islamic Law and Society
34	M.A. Fay	Women and Waqf: Toward a Reconsideration of Women's Place in The Mamluk Household	1997	Int. J. Middle East Stud
28	O. Peri	Waqf and Ottoman Welfare Policy. The Poor Kitchen of Hasseki Sultan in Eighteenth-Century	1992	Source: Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient

The highest cited paper belongs to T. Kuran [13] with 156 citations. Article titles "The Provision of Public Goods under Islamic Law: Origins, Impact, and imitations of the Waqf System" was published in 2001 in Journal of the Law and Society Association. Most cited papers on waqf are historical study on the concept and implementation of waqf practices. Among period studied varied from the 16th century (Baer, [7]) Ottoman Empire (Mandaville, [14]; Peri, [22]; and Yayla, [33]) and Syiria (Doumani, [8]) in the 18th, and The Mamluk (Fay, [9]). The idea of cash waqf and its controversy has been published in 1979; Mohsin then discuss on how waqf could be made as source of financing in 2013.

From all publications, those with the highest number of zakat articles is as follow:

Table 3

Top Publication based on Number of Zakat Articles

Number	Publication
15	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
10	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management
6	International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology
6	Jurnal Pengurusan
5	Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development

Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research has 15 articles with the word "zakat" on the title. Most of articles are conceptual paper, such as Mutamimah (2021), Obaidullah (2016), Owoyemi (2018), Wahab [32], Wahab et.al (2017), and Zauro, N A [36], and one bibliometric analysis on zakat (Alshater, 2021). The rest are empirical papers, such as Andam & Osman (2019), Nashwan et.al (2021), Kashif et.al (2018), Mustafa et.al (2013), Saad (2020), and Mohd Thas Thaker (2021).

International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management has the most publication on zakat with 15 articles. Most of the articles are empirical papers such as Djaghballou (2018), Farouk et.al (2018), Mahmud et. al (2014), Rahmat & Nurzaman (2019), Sanusi (2014), Shabbir (2018), Usman & Rahman (2021), and Wahyuni, et.al (2021). There is one text mining oz zakat articles (Hudaefi et.al, 2021). The others are conceptual papers, such as Adnan & Bakar (2009), Haneef et.al (2015), Mohsin (2013), Rahman (2015).

Table 4

Top Publication based on Number of Waqf Articles

Number	Journal
14	ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance
11	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
7	Humanomics
7	Islamic Law and Society
5	Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient
5	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah

ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance has 11 articles on waqf. Most of the articles are conceptual papers such as Abdullah (2020), Hasan (2019), Khan (2019), Laallam et.al (2020), Mikail et.al (2017), Izzati & Ishak (2021), Shaikh et.al (2017), Sulaiman et.al (2019), Mohd Thas Thaker (2018a), Abdul Rais (2018), and Kachkar (2017). Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research has 8 articles. One is bibliometric study (Uluyolet.al, 2021), two empirical papers: Asni et.al (2020), Azmi & Hanifa (2015); and others are conceptual studies: Abdullah (2019), Mohd Thas Thaker & Pitchay (2018a), Mohd Thas Thaker et.al (2016a), Osman & Agyemang (2020), Sulaiman & Zakari (2019).

R.A. Jaffri Saad is most author with eight papers related to zakat issue. He wrote both conceptual and empirical papers with various conceptual topics such as issue on functional zakat system, zakat institution governance, zakat surplus management; and empirical studies on compliance behavior and zakat management. Norazlina Abd. Wahab followed by six papers mainly studying on zakat institution efficiency and quality.

M.A.B. Mohd Thas Thaker is most author with eight papers related to waqf issue. He wrote both conceptual and empirical papers. Among the main topics of the study is on whether waqf could be made as source of financing. D. Crecelius, K. Khalfan, and M. Abdullah each contributes three articles related to the issue.

Table 5

Top Zakat First Authors based on Number of Articles

Authors	N	Title	Cites	Source
R.A. Jaffri Saad	8	A comprehensive review of barriers to a functional Zakat system in Nigeria: What needs to be done?	10	International Journal of Ethics and Systems
		Factors that influenced the Business Zakah Compliance Behaviour	9	Jurnal Pengurusan
		Governance of non-profit organizations: A case of zakat institutions in Malaysia	6	International Journal of Economic Research
		Business zakat compliance behavioral intention in a developing country	5	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
		Zakat surplus funds management	4	International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues
		What influence entrepreneur to pay Islamic tax (Zakat)?	3	Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal
		Factors affecting and means of managing zakat surplus in Malaysia	3	Information (Japan)
		Perceived service quality of zakat institution among Muslim businessmen in Malaysia.	0	AIP Conference Proceeding
Norazlina Abd. Wahab	6	A framework to analyse the efficiency and governance of zakat institutions	53	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
		Efficiency of zakat institutions in Malaysia: An application of data envelopment analysis	19	Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development
		Determinants of efficiency of zakat institutions in Malaysia: A non-parametric approach	11	Asian Journal of Business and Accounting
		Developing service quality index for zakat institutions	2	International Journal of
		Productivity growth of zakat institutions in Malaysia: An application of data envelopment analysis	8	Studies in Economics and Finance
		Towards developing service quality index for zakat institutions	5	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
C.M. Doktoralina	3	Role of accounting Zakat as a support function in supply chain management: A resurrection of the Islamic economy	4	International Journal of Supply Chain Management
		Hashtags as a way to expedite the zakat supply chain	4	Uncertain Supply Chain Management
		Zakat accounting information system in private higher education	1	European Research Studies Journal

Fuadah Johari	3	Zakat distribution and programme forsustaining muallaf belief and thought	6	Jurnal Teknologi (Sciences and Engineering)
		The roles of islamic social welfare assistant (zakat) for the economic development of new convert	5	Middle East Journal of Scientific Research
		The importance of zakat distribution and urban-rural poverty incidence among Muallaf (new convert)	4	Asian Social Science

Table 6

Top Waqf First Authors based on Number of Articles

No	Authors	Title	Cites	Year	Source
8	M.A.B. Mohd Thas Thaker	Factors influencing the adoption of the crowdfunding-waqf model (CWM) in the waqf land development	22	2018	Journal of Islamic Marketing
		A qualitative inquiry into cash waqf model as a source of financing for micro enterprises	10	2018	ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance
		A qualitative inquiry into cash waqf model as a source of financing for micro enterprises	52	2018	ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance
		Developing waqf land through crowdfunding-waqf model (CWM): the case of Malaysia	2	2018	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
		Developing cash waqf model as an alternative source of financing for micro enterprises in Malaysia	12	2016	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research
		The Behavioral Intention of Micro Enterprises to Use the Integrated Cash Waqf Micro Enterprise Investment (ICWME-I) Model as a Source of Financing	7	2016	Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business
		Exploring the Contemporary Issues of Corporate Share Waqf Model in Malaysia with the Reference to the Waqaf An-Nur Corporation Berhad (Menerokai Isu-Isu Semasa Model Wakaf Saham Korporat di Malaysia dengan Rujukan kepada Waqaf An-Nur Corporation Berhad)	19	2015	Jurnal Pengurusan
		Modeling crowdfunder's behavioral intention to adopt the crowdfunding-waqf model (CWM) in Malaysia: The theory of the technology acceptance model	17	2018	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management
3	D. Crecelius	Incidences of Waqf Cases in Three Cairo	21	1986	Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient
		The Waqf Of Muhammad Bey Abu Al-Dhahabin Historical Perspective	19	1991	International Journal of Middle East Studies

Zakat articles clusters mapping is as follow:

1. Cluster 1 consist of 24 keywords: addition, attention, author, design methodology approach, economic growth, effect, evidence, factor, impact, income, knowledge, muslim country, originality value, performance, practical implication, questionnaire, relationship, research limitations implication, researcher, respondent, sample, theory, zakat payer, zakat payment.
2. Cluster 2 consist of 20 keywords: article, beneficiary, case study, community, concept, economy, effectiveness, fact, form, fund, importance, information, interview, order, poverty alleviation, source, welfare, zakat distribution, zakat management, zakat recipient.
3. Cluster 3 consist of 19 keywords: amount, application, asset, charity, individual, islam, lack, muslim, muslims, needy, obligation, Pakistan, part, person, pillar, system, trust, year, zakat system.

There are three cluster from zakat articles. First cluster related to design methodology approach and the terms related. We can infer that there are quite significant number of empirical papers. Cluster two related to the objective or the focus of the study covering zakat management and how it is related to the economy and welfare. Cluster three could be related to issues on conceptual papers. It is interesting that Pakistan is mentioned on cluster three, even though most papers are studying on Malaysia case.

Figure 4 VosViewer Graphical and Clustering Visualization for Waqf Articles

Waqf articles clusters mapping is as follow:

1. Cluster 1 consist of 31 keywords: article authority, basis, building, charity, community, concept, creation, economy, education, establishment, founder, history, individual, Islam, land, muslim, muslims, order, person, potential, poverty, process, property, question, revenue, student, time, understanding, view
2. Cluster 2 consist of 16 keywords: accountability, aspect, author, case study, design methodology approach, donor, framework, lack, originality value, practical implication, research limitations implication, social implication, stakeholder, sustainability, waqf institution, waqf management.
3. Cluster 3 consist of 12 keywords: addition, asset, factor, financing, future research, implementation, light, number, type, use, waqf land, waqf property.

There are three clusters resulted from waqf articles. First cluster is related to the focus of the discussion; keywords mentioned are both related to conceptual and empirical papers. Second cluster is related to design methodology approach and the operational framework of the studies. Third cluster is related to subjects to discuss for future research; waqf land and waqf property are still important to be discussed and waqf as source of financing is getting more attention as some papers are proposing on that.

Figure 5 VosViewer Graphical and Clustering Visualization for Zakat and Waqf Articles

Zakat and waqf combined articles clusters mapping is as follow:

1. Cluster 1 consist of 38 keywords: accountability, action, area, attitude, author, case study, cash waqf, design methodology approach, donor, factor, financing, future research, influence, insight, knowledge, lack, light, literature, muslim country, originality value, perception, performance, policy maker, practical implication, present study, primary data, questionnaire, relationship, research limitations, implication, respondent, sample, social implication, stakeholder, survey, sustainability, theory, waqf institution, waqf land.
2. Cluster 2 consist of 38 keywords: amount, charity, community, distribution, economic growth, education, effect, effectiveness, evidence, fact, guideline, hand, individual, Indonesia, Islam, muslim, muslim society, muslims, needy, obligation, Pakistan, payment, person, pillar, poverty, recipient, regulation, religion, wealth, welfare, year, zakat, zakat collection, zakat distribution, zakat fund, zakat institution, zakat recipient, zakat system.
3. Cluster 3 consist of 34 keywords: application, article, attempt, challenge, change, concept, content analysis, creation, element, endowment, establishment, example, form, founder, Islamic law, land, law, nature, part, period, principle, process, property, provision, question, reason, responsibility, revenue, rule, structure, time, type, waqf, waqf property.

When all zakat and waqf articles are combined, there are three main clusters: zakat, waqf, and design methodology approach. Each item under zakat and waqf mapping cluster is related to objective and operational variables of the study. Cluster of design methodology approach shows that the number of both conceptual and empirical papers are significant.

Table 7

Top Authors based on Number of Articles

Author	Articles	Total Link strength
Johari,Fuadah	9	14
Mohd Thas Thaker, Mohamed Asmy Bin	9	9
Saad, Ram Al Jaffri	7	5
Saiti, Buerhan	5	3
Mohammed, Mustafa Omar	4	7
Bahari, Zakaria	4	6
Doktoralina, Caturida Meiwanto	4	6
Allah Pitchay, Anwar	4	3

In total, Johari wrote the most articles. Be it first or co-authors, Johari has nine documents. She writes articles on zakat and waqf, mostly conceptual papers. She also has the highest link strength on articles related to zakat and waqf. Three of her papers discuss on zakat for muallaf (new convert). Mohd Thas Thaker writes all nine articles on waqf, some on cash waqf and how it could be made as source of financing for microfinance.

Table 8

Top Authors based on Total Link Strength

Author	Articles	Total Link strength
Johari, Fuadah	9	14
Mohd Thas Thaker, Mohamed Asmy Bin	9	9
Amin, Hanudin	3	8
Aziz, Muhammad Ridhwan Ab	3	8
Abdul-Rahman, Abdul-Rahim	2	8
Mohd-Aris, Masmurniwati	2	8
Ramayah, T	2	8
Supinah, Rostinah	2	8
Mohammed, Mustafa Omar	4	7
Samargandi, Nahla	3	7
Buchner, Elmar	2	7
Schmieder, Martin	2	7

Based on total link strength, Johari has the highest one with 14 links. Mohd Thas Thaker is the next with nine total link strengths. Johari and Mohd Thas Thaker are on the top list on the most documents and link strength on research related to zakat and waqf. They have several co authorship with other researchers who also write on topics of zakat and waqf

DISCUSSION

This study focuses on the trend of research articles related to Islamic social finance. "Zakat" and "waqf" are chosen as the keywords that should be found on the title of the documents to be included on the analysis. Previous studies focus on either zakat or waqf only. This study combines both for the similarity of both keywords as both are categorized as Islamic social finance.

Before 2000, Scopus documented maximum one publication per year in some years for articles titled zakat. Waqf has slightly more documents; the record has two publications under the title in 1991 and 1995, three in 1998, and six in 1997. Both zakat and waqf number of articles are fluctuating after that and reach the peak in 2018.

Top article titled "zakat" with highest citation number dated back in 1987. The topic is on resistance to zakat. It could be inferred that there are quite significant amount of zakat articles discussing on perception or behavior towards zakat. Top cited article titled "waqf" has higher number of citation but with later publication in 2001. The topic is on the waqf concept. As waqf in concept has more flexibility compared to zakat, it seems that there are quite a number of studies discussing on waqf concept and proposing possible innovative waqf models within the original context.

Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research (JIABR) has the highest number of publications related to Islamic social finance by 15 articles titled zakat and 9 articles titled waqf. JIABR articles on zakat are dominated by conceptual papers while JIABR waqf articles are mostly empirical studies.

Ram Al Jaffri Saad from University Utara Malaysia has the most zakat articles indexed on Scopus database as the first author. Norazlina Abd Wahab with the same university affiliation is the second best with six articles. On waqf articles, Mohamed Asmy bin Mohd Thas Thaker from International Islamic University Malaysia is the first author with the highest publication by 8 articles.

Vosviewer result shows interesting result when the articles are separated between zakat and waqf papers and when they are combined. When they are analysed separately, both zakat and waqf has three clusters mapping. Similar result happens when they are analysed overall. When analysed separately, each cluster mapping represents the object of the study, the design methodology approach, and the operational variables used on the analysis. Upon combined articles, Islamic social finance in total is divided into main issue on zakat, main issue on waqf, and research method used.

Pakistan is the only country mentioned on the cluster mapping, under articles titled "zakat." Other zakat articles studying on Pakistan context are Clark (2001), Jehle (1994), Mohammad (2016), and Shaikh (2015, 2017). There are also waqf articles studying on Pakistan such as Usman et.al (2021) and Richardson (2010).

Malaysia is the most favorite object of study for both zakat and waqf. There are significant number of authors based in Malaysia institutions. Among zakat articles

are: Rosli et.al (2018), Mohit (2011), Ab Rahman [1], Ali [4], Ali (2016), Al Ma'mun et. al(2020), Aziz & Ali (2018), Azman et.al (2015), Basir et.al (2017), Yusuf (2013), Saad & Sawandi (2016), Abd Wahab & Abdul (2013), Abd Wahab & Rahman (2012), Abd Wahab (2012), Abashah et. al (2018), Abdullah & Sapiei (2018), Adnan et.al (2013, 2019), Afroz (2019), Ahmad (2011), Hamat (2014), Hasan (2019), Lateff (2014), Muller (2017), Rahman et.al (2012), Rasool et.al (2011), Razak (2020), Rosman et.al (1967), Ryandono et.al (2020), Samad & Said (2016), Samad & Nassir (2016), Samargandi et.al (2018), Sulaiman (2015a, 2015b), Steiner (2012), Sharofiddin (1967), Yusuf (2013), and Wahid (2014). While waqf articles studying Malaysian context are: Daud (2019), Embong (2013), Hisyam et. al (2013), Ibrahim et.al (2016), Ismail (2015), Khairi et.al (2014), Khan et.al (2020), Mohd Thas Thaker & Mohd Thas Thaker (2015), Mohd Thas Thaker et.al (2016), Mohd Thas Thaker et.al (2018a,b). Pitchay et.al (2018), Shabbir & Malik (2018), Noor (2014), Nu et.al (2013), Omar et.al (2021), Rahman et.al (2011), Sanusi et.al (2014), Sulaiman & Zakari (2019), Suhaimi et.al (2014), Shahimi et.al (2013), Shahedur et.al (2012a, 2012b), Talib (2018), and Zain et.al (2020).

Indonesia is the second most research object of study on zakat and waqf. Among those zakat studies are: Wahyuni et.al (2012), Sukmana et.al (2021), Saidurrahman (2013), Rini & Fatimah (2019), Ridwan et.al (2019a, 2019b), Mutamimah et.al (2021), Kusriyah (2020), Kailani (2020), Jermsttiparsert & Sommanawat (2019), Jahar (2015), Hudaefi et.al [11], Huda et.al (2017), Hariyanto et.al (2020), Mohd (2018), Halimatussa'diyah (2015), Fikriyah et.al (2019), Cokrohadisumarto (2020), Auliyah & Basuki (2021), Amilahaq et.al (2021), Amalia (2019), Ali (2014), and Abdullah (2018). While waqf researches with Indonesia as the object are: Siswantoro et.al (2018), Shulthoni & Saad (2018), Rosadi et.al (2013), Retsikas (2014), Ihsan et.al (2017), Ihsan & Ibrahim (2011), and Hariyanto et.al (2020).

There are articles studying on zakat in Bangladesh such as Sohag et.al (2015), Mahmud et.al (2014), Begum (1993), and Ali [4]; and on waqf such as Hassan et.al (2019) and Haneef et.al (2015). Other waqf studies are in Egypt such as Crecelius (1986, 1971), Shaham (1998), and Hathaway (1994). Other countries mentioned on the articles are Nigeria such as Zauro et.al [37], Farouq et.al (2018), and Ahmad (2019), Philippines such as Andam & Osman (2019), Gamon & Tagoranao (2018), Algeria (Djaghballou, 2018), and Brunei (Salleh, 2015).

Some of the research proposing models for zakat management such as Clark (2001), Ahmed (2016), and Ahmad (2011). Some others propose innovative models for waqf scheme both cash waqf and fixed asset waqf such as Mohammed et.al (2017) Abdul Rais (2018), Zakaria et.al (2013); Sulaiman et.al (2019), Shamsudin et.al

(2015), Haneef et.al (2015), Hassan (2014) Mohd Thas Thaker (2018a), and Asni et.al (2020). Some other research are related to maqasid such as Zakaria (2014), Arshad et.al (2018), and Abdullah (2018).

Latest issue related to Islamic social finance is related to the integration idea between Islamic social finance with commercial finance. Among those studies are: Zauro et.al (2020a, 2020b), Zabri & Mohammed (2018), Mohd Thas Thaker et.al (2016); Shamsudin et.al (2015), Hassan (2014) Haneef et.al (2015), Ari & Koc (2021), and Mikail et.al (2017).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Research related on Islamic social finance covers wide variety of topics. Both development of zakat and waqf related discussion has been progressing and the number of research studying these issues are rising.

Since the emergence of COVID-19, the study on finding alternative source of financing is increasing. Integration of commercial and social finance could be among the solutions. Therefore, it needs to be studied more to propose new and more innovative models. Future discussion on positioning zakat and waqf as formal national source of financing is still needed. Methods and points of discussion on zakat and waqf in other countries could adopt and imitate those implemented in countries which have been studied frequently such as Malaysia and Indonesia.

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